

Gender Perception of Static Contents Based on Pupil Dilation in Cognitive Response

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Abstract

Research ([1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]) has shown that the eyes are the windows to the soul, and the pupils are the gateway to the brain. When a person's eyes set sight on things around them, they normally track different features around them ; both the corneas of the eyes and tissues surrounding the lenses adjust to focus on the light that conveys a scene visible to the scene around them. The pupil changes are also a measure of the cognitive load in a person and this paper tends to address the level of cognition in a person based on gender effects and the cognitive level in visual perception from static contents of the visual scene to area of interest. The cognitive level is based on the average, complex, neutral, relaxed, and stressful mood of a person and these are measured based and sequential values assigned as classes of cognitive level that represent the cognition level of a person. An error was computed for each trial and the result shows that the Average and complex mood of the user in reaction to the static contents is more predicted in the other set class of cognitive level both on the male and female gender than when the gender is mixed. These results can be reflected in the response pupil behaviour of the eye movement on the static contents.

Keywords : *Pupil changes, Cognitive level, Visual experience, Light intensity, Stimulus*

1 Introduction

The pupil changes are a measure of the Pupillometry of the eyes. It gives a unique insight into how a person views the environment. Studies ([10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18])

from pop science show that the pupil dilates in response to positive and attractive stimuli ; psychologists reveal that both positive and negative valence information can produce an increase in pupil response in reaction to complex visual contents.

Research ([19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26]) has established that emotional response with a high level of charged stimuli such as images, sounds, and words can elicit an expansion of pupil sizes that changes with time. This provides a measure of emotional response that is both dissimilar and diverse from galvanic skin response that represents the intensity of emotional response uncovered without focus. Other research ([27, 28, 29, 30]) has also suggested that the pupillometry response test is a more reliable measure of a stress-related reaction than the GSR and has more constraints on how the studies are been carried out. Other research ([31, 32, 33, 34]) has also disclosed the cognitive load as a link to the degree of pupil dilation and this occurs with different cognitive demand tasks that is similar to an increase in great size as the pupil size e.g. in a Stroop task, participants read incongruent colored words such as words written in “blue” and printed in “red” color. These research findings suggest that an increase in pupil dilation is synchronous to an increase in cognitive processes i.e. the harder a person’s brain works and reacts to process information; leading to a great increase in pupil size (Figure 1).

2 Literature Review

Most research on fMRI ([35, 36, 37]), found that increases in brain activity that is within the different areas of the head have been directly attached to pupil dilation, making this measure a perfect proxy for comprehending the cognitive processes at a higher level in cognition. Research in the clinical and medical area ([38, 39, 40, 41]) has also found that abnormal pupillometry responses to basic stimuli in a person are related to depression, spectrum disorder, anxiety, and autism. These are of critical importance to the measure of pupil size, not only for understanding normal body function but also for what goes on in the brain of a person afflicted with certain diseases. This offers some tentative ideas as to how a person suffering from a neurological kind of disease might be able to improve their condition. Furthermore, researchers have noted that psychological treatment could be successful when predicted at a certain level which depends on the pupillometry results. And can help to provide easy means or ways to ensure the best possible treatment that matches that of an afflicted person based on simulation; this can help improve recovery rates and also efficient health care processes. The field of brain-computer interaction could also greatly enhance the utilisation of pupil dilation as a means of single processing, which is adapted for people with physical movement impairments. Eye tracking can also be a means to access computer interaction and improved ergonomics by bringing a more reliable measure of pupil size as an additional cognitive signal that is included and inspirational to the brain-computer processes.

Graur and Ziegler ([42, 43, 44]) in their article state

that the combined use of other biosensors and pupil measures can take the human-computer interaction even further into the field of cognition in humans to a more advanced stage of discovery in the knowledge of how the brain processes work in visual activities based on behaviour patterns. In some cases when a personal computer can perceive a user’s emotion through the use of physiological measures like galvanic skin response and heart rate combined with pupil diameter measure, visual perception can intelligently alter the user’s experience.

2.1 Pupil Measure Procedure

To discover new mechanics in pupillometry, one needs an eye tracker, a stimulus of any choice, depending on the form of research. Recent studies have also investigated novel techniques for pupil measuring using a local webcam embedded in PCs as a non-invasive measure. It is also possible to get it up and running using specified modules that track the eye movement on a visual scene. Other pupillometry devices ([45, 46, 47]) are required as eye trackers can also perform the function, these devices are utilised for cost reduction purposes and can work as perfectly as the device specifically designed for pupil tracking. The major parameter to be controlled in most pupil measures is the amount of light that is naked to the participant’s view. The measure of the pupil size is the changes in visual light intensity V_m , which is the absolute sum of the light intensity l_i directed to a person’s vision Equation 1 (Figure 2). The standardisation of the stimuli luminescence must be ensured and any pupil reflection is due to the emotional and cognitive response to the stimulus and this is not similar to a purely physical reaction to light intensity.

$$\frac{dV_m}{dt} = \frac{1}{c_m} \sum_{i=1}^n l_i \quad (1)$$

3 Method

The factor to be controlled in pupil measure experimental set-up is the lighting levels in the room which are also additional external factors. To get the most from the pupil measure data, it is possible the benefit more by including other biosensors that complement the findings. For this research, the Moving average filter (MovAFilter) (Equation 2) is used, not only as a form of signal propagation and smoothing but also to complement the response to stimuli with an equal reaction. This measure is automatically calculated in the procedures and commences the steps in comprehending the underlying cause of the increased pupil dilation in a simplified term. This is given as :

$$MovA_{filter} = \frac{A_1 + A_2 + \dots + A_n}{n} \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 1 – As the amount of cognitive or emotional processing increases, so does the pupil dilation. Courtesy : (Google images).

FIGURE 2 – The Three most essential stimuli that increase pupil dilation are light, emotional stimuli, and information that increases cognitive load.

where

$$A = C - P\left(\frac{2}{n+1} + P\right) \quad (3)$$

P and C are the external constraints due to atmospheric pressure, this additional physiological measure though similar can be a virtual version of the reaction to stimuli and this can enrich the understanding of a person's thoughts and cognitive level based on behaviour. The data used in this study is derived from a predefined experiment saved in an archive that consists of participants' demographic data and user interaction with static contents of webpages. The participants were grouped into three, male gender (20), female gender (30), and mixed gender (both female and male (40)). Their pupil changes and eye movements were synchronised and recorded. Figure 3 shows a synchronised session of webpage stimuli containing static contents and eye-tracking gaze points with pupil dilation and virtual representation of pupil response from the study. The cognitive level of the

participants is based on the set values assigned to this level of cognition (Table ??). To determine this level the response to a significant event has to be synchronous to the virtual representation of the pupil changes significantly to a static point in the Area of interest (AOI). The performance and rate of cognitive recognition can be computed and compared to other levels of cognition in a person. The proceeding section discusses the results obtained from the analysis of data generated from the experiment.

4 Result

Figure 4 shows the raw pupil response and virtual pupil measure as the moving average filter that complements the original pupil response. The raw signal and smooth signal indicate little difference in signal flow ; the major significant event occurred between one to 90 seconds to the session for the female gender and one to

TABLE 1 – The class of cognitive level assigned to both female and male in response to presented stimuli.

Male Gender					Female Gender				
Complex	Average	Relaxed	Neutral	Stress	Complex	Average	Relaxed	Neutral	Stress
2.0	6.0	9.0	5.0	2.0	3.0	6.0	8.0	5.0	7.0
2.0	6.0	9.0	5.0	2.0	3.0	6.0	8.0	5.0	7.0

sixty seconds into the male gender session. While the raw seems quite straightforward, the module for simulating the behaviour strikes one as rather complex and inaccessible. A simple view on this is simple use a five-second minimum distance for every iteration and this will produce a smooth well-readable and meaningful data sequence that is interpretable. These are fed into predictive models to determine their accuracy and density function.

Figure 5 shows that the pupil changes in density between the sessions and grows with magnitude towards the end of the session. This is indicated in the intersection of constriction of the pupil during response intensity and dilation of the pupil during response relaxation, i.e. the pupil tends to dilate more when the response intensity is high on the virtual static contents (Figure 5b). an average response can produce a density function of 0.3 between 2-2.5 seconds into the session. This also coincides with the idea that response stimulus normally occurs between 0 to 3 seconds into any typical session. There is, however, equal density in response to both dilation and constriction (Figure 5c) in terms of reaction to web static contents, other stimuli like video sequencing might have a different effect.

The pupil's function is response to environment stimuli presented to a person's eyes and the process of the reaction normally reflects the cognitive processes. The error plot in Figure 6, shows errors computed from the inner workings and computations in the mind. The stimulus was designed to have these classes of cognitive levels in reaction to static contents from a webpage presented to the participants. The error in measurement shows that stress is the most significant cognitive level in a person when viewing static contents ; i.e. a person might not even notice he is stressed during the interaction as the pupil changes show the underlying response to stress. The error for stress to relaxed mood is between 0.01 to 0.1%. A negative computed error can also be termed as an absolute inclusive error in measure when it comes to pupil behavioural response to visual content.

5 Conclusion

The pupil measure is a suitable measure for understanding the intenseness of the stimuli, as cognitive and emotional processing, and this is relevant for further understanding of the complex visual stimuli for advanced user experience based on psychological testing and more.

This paper attempts to investigate pupil measure of cognitive level on gender perception of static contents, the measure of pupil dilation is a pupillometry that gives unique insights into how an individual views their environment. The pupil changes are also a measure of the cognitive load in a person and this paper tends to address how the level of cognition in a person based on gender affects the cognitive level in visual perception from static contents of the visual scene. The cognitive level is based on the average, complex, neutral, relaxed, and stressful mood of a person and these are measured based and sequential values assigned as classes of cognitive level that represent the cognition of a person. The error was computed for each trial and the result shows that the Average and complex mood of the user in reaction to the static contents is more predicted in the other set class of cognitive level both on the male and female gender than when the genders are mixed. These results can be reflected in the response pupil behaviour of the eye movement on the static contents. Further research would be to learn more about pupil dilation and how its measure in eye tracing can be used within user behaviour modelling research.

Acknowledgement

The authors would wish to thank Nasarawa State University and Metro science academy for their contribution to this study with regard to user behaviour modelling and data acquisition.

Références

- [1] Ferencova, N., Visnovcova, Z., Olexova, L. B., & Tonhajzerova, I. (2021). Eye pupil—a window into central autonomic regulation via emotional/cognitive processing. *Physiological Research*, 70(Suppl 4), S669.
- [2] Shoyombo, I., Aiyagari, V., Stutzman, S. E., Atem, F., Hill, M., Figueroa, S. A., ... & Olson, D. M. (2018). Understanding the relationship between the neurologic pupil index and constriction velocity values. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), 1-6.
- [3] Shoyombo, I., Aiyagari, V., Stutzman, S. E., Atem, F., Hill, M., Figueroa, S. A., ... & Olson, D. M. (2018). Understanding the relationship between the neurologic pupil index and constriction velocity values. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), 1-6.

- [4] Laeng, B., Eidet, L. M., Sulutvedt, U., & Panksepp, J. (2016). Music chills : The eye pupil as a mirror to music's soul. *Consciousness and cognition*, 44, 161-178.
- [5] McGinley, M. J. (2020). Brain states : Sensory modulations all the way down. *Current Biology*, 30(20), R1263-R1266.
- [6] Ang, J. L., Collis, S., Dhillon, B., & Cackett, P. (2021). The Eye in Forensic Medicine : A Narrative Review. *The Asia-Pacific Journal of Ophthalmology*, 10(5), 486-494.
- [7] Reilly, J., Zuckerman, B., & Kelly, A. (2021). A Primer on Design and Data Analysis for Cognitive Pupillometry.
- [8] Quirins, M., Marois, C., Valente, M., Seassau, M., Weiss, N., El Karoui, I., ... & Naccache, L. (2018). Conscious processing of auditory regularities induces a pupil dilation. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), 1-11.
- [9] White, O. B., & Costello, F. (2017). Melanopsin effects on pupil responses : Is the eye the window to the weary soul?. *JAMA neurology*, 74(5), 506-508.
- [10] Hess, E. H. (1975). The role of pupil size in communication. *Scientific American*, 233(5), 110-119.
- [11] Matyjek, M., Bayer, M., & Dziobek, I. (2021). Pupillary responses to faces are modulated by familiarity and rewarding context. *Brain sciences*, 11(6), 794.
- [12] Kuraguchi, K., & Kanari, K. (2021). Enlargement of female pupils when perceiving something cute. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 1-10.
- [13] Zekveld, A. A., Koelewijn, T., & Kramer, S. E. (2018). The pupil dilation response to auditory stimuli : Current state of knowledge. *Trends in hearing*, 22, 2331216518777174.
- [14] Hess, E. H., & Petrovich, S. B. (1987). Pupillary behavior in communication. *Nonverbal behavior and communication*, 327-348.
- [15] Attard-Johnson, J., Bindemann, M., & Ó Ciardha, C. (2016). Pupillary response as an age-specific measure of sexual interest. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 45(4), 855-870.
- [16] Tummeltshammer, K., Feldman, E. C., & Amso, D. (2019). Using pupil dilation, eye-blink rate, and the value of mother to investigate reward learning mechanisms in infancy. *Developmental cognitive neuroscience*, 36, 100608.
- [17] Zhu, X., Qin, Z., Gedeon, T., Jones, R., Hossain, M. Z., & Caldwell, S. (2018, December). Detecting the doubt effect and subjective beliefs using neural networks and observers' pupillary responses. In *International Conference on Neural Information Processing* (pp. 610-621). Springer, Cham.
- [18] Czajka, A. (2015). Pupil dynamics for iris liveness detection. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 10(4), 726-735.
- [19] Slovák, M., Anýž, J., Erlebach, J., Sieger, T., Forejtová, Z., Fabián, V., ... & Serranová, T. (2022). Emotional arousal in patients with functional movement disorders : A pupillometry study. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 111043.
- [20] Oliva, M., & Anikin, A. (2018). Pupil dilation reflects the time course of emotion recognition in human vocalizations. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), 1-10.
- [21] Strauch, C., Wang, C. A., Einhäuser, W., Van der Stigchel, S., & Naber, M. (2022). Pupillometry as an integrated readout of distinct attentional networks. *Trends in Neurosciences*.
- [22] Bradley, M. M., Sambuco, N., & Lang, P. J. (2022). Affective Perception : The Power Is in the Picture. In *Human Perception of Visual Information* (pp. 59-83). Springer, Cham.
- [23] Zsidó, A. N., Stecina, D. T., & Hout, M. C. (2022). Task demands determine whether shape or arousal of a stimulus modulates competition for visual working memory resources. *Acta Psychologica*, 224, 103523.
- [24] Parvizi, J., Veit, M. J., Barbosa, D. A., Kucyi, A., Perry, C., Parker, J. J., ... & Halpern, C. H. (2022). Complex negative emotions induced by electrical stimulation of the human hypothalamus. *Brain Stimulation*, 15(3), 615-623.
- [25] Li, Y., Kim, H. J., Do, B., & Choi, J. (2022). The effect of emotion in thumbnails and titles of video clips on pre-roll advertising effectiveness. *Journal of Business Research*, 151, 232-243.
- [26] Martinez-Levy, A. C., Rossi, D., Cartocci, G., Mancini, M., Di Flumeri, G., Trettel, A., ... & Cherubino, P. (2022). Message framing, non-conscious perception and effectiveness in non-profit advertising. Contribution by neuromarketing research. *International Review on Public and Nonprofit Marketing*, 19(1), 53-75.
- [27] Collins, A., Scott, R. B., Hirsch, C. R., Ottaviani, C., Krahe, C., & Meeten, F. (2022). A systematic review of the literature on interpretation bias and its physiological correlates. *Biological psychology*, 108398.
- [28] Fietz, J., Pöhlchen, D., Binder, F. P., BeCOME Working Group, Czisch, M., Sämann, P. G., & Spoor-maker, V. I. (2022). Pupillometry tracks cognitive load and salience network activity in a working memory functional magnetic resonance imaging task. *Human brain mapping*, 43(2), 665-680.
- [29] Slovák, M., Anýž, J., Erlebach, J., Sieger, T., Forejtová, Z., Fabián, V., ... & Serranová, T. (2022). Emotional arousal in patients with functional movement disorders : A pupillometry study. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 111043.
- [30] Zhao, S., Liu, Y., & Wei, K. (2022). Pupil-Linked Arousal Response Reveals Aberrant Attention Regulation among Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 42(27), 5427-5437.

- [31] Souchet, A. D., Philippe, S., Lourdeaux, D., & Leroy, L. (2022). Measuring visual fatigue and cognitive load via eye tracking while learning with virtual reality head-mounted displays : A review. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 38(9), 801-824.
- [32] Bauer, R., Jost, L., Günther, B., & Jansen, P. (2022). Pupillometry as a measure of cognitive load in mental rotation tasks with abstract and embodied figures. *Psychological Research*, 86(5), 1382-1396.
- [33] Zheng, Z., Gao, S., Su, Y., Chen, Y., & Wang, X. (2022). Cognitive load-induced pupil dilation reflects potential flight ability. *Current Psychology*, 1-11.
- [34] Choi, Y., & Lee, H. (2022). Psychometric Properties for Multidimensional Cognitive Load Scale in an E-Learning Environment. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(10), 5822.
- [35] Rocchi, F., Canella, C., Noei, S., Gutierrez-Barragan, D., Coletta, L., Galbusera, A., ... & Gozzi, A. (2022). Increased fMRI connectivity upon chemogenetic inhibition of the mouse prefrontal cortex. *Nature communications*, 13(1), 1-15.
- [36] Logothetis, N. K., Pauls, J., Augath, M., Trinath, T., & Oeltermann, A. (2001). Neurophysiological investigation of the basis of the fMRI signal. *nature*, 412(6843), 150-157.
- [37] Allen, E. J., St-Yves, G., Wu, Y., Breedlove, J. L., Prince, J. S., Dowdle, L. T., ... & Kay, K. (2022). A massive 7T fMRI dataset to bridge cognitive neuroscience and artificial intelligence. *Nature neuroscience*, 25(1), 116-126.
- [38] Slovák, M., Anýž, J., Erlebach, J., Sieger, T., Forejtová, Z., Fabián, V., ... & Serranová, T. (2022). Emotional arousal in patients with functional movement disorders : A pupillometry study. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 111043.
- [39] DiNuzzo, M., Mangia, S., Moraschi, M., Mascali, D., Hagberg, G. E., & Giove, F. (2022). Perception is associated with the brain's metabolic response to sensory stimulation. *Elife*, 11.
- [40] Hong, L., He, H., & Sajda, P. (2022). Pupil-linked phasic arousal relates to the reduction of response inhibition : inferences from a simultaneous pupillometry and EEG-fMRI study. *bioRxiv*.
- [41] Zhao, S., Liu, Y., & Wei, K. (2022). Pupil-Linked Arousal Response Reveals Aberrant Attention Regulation among Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 42(27), 5427-5437.
- [42] Naibert, N., & Barbera, J. (2022). Development and Evaluation of a Survey to Measure Student Engagement at the Activity Level in General Chemistry. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 99(3), 1410-1419.
- [43] Cristea, C., Graur, F., Gălătuș, R., Vaida, C., Pislă, D., & Săndulescu, R. (2018). Nanobiomaterials for cancer diagnosis and therapy. In *Nanobiomaterials* (pp. 329-375). Apple Academic Press.
- [44] Muller, L., Sinn, S., Drechsel, H., Ziegler, C., Wendel, H. P., Northoff, H., & Gehring, F. K. (2010). Investigation of prothrombin time in human whole-blood samples with a quartz crystal biosensor. *Analytical chemistry*, 82(2), 658-663.
- [45] McIntire, L. K., McIntire, J. P., McKinley, R. A., & Goodyear, C. (2014, March). Detection of vigilance performance with pupillometry. In *Proceedings of the symposium on eye tracking research and applications* (pp. 167-174).
- [46] Zheng, L. J., Mountstephens, J., & Teo, J. (2020). Four-class emotion classification in virtual reality using pupillometry. *Journal of Big Data*, 7(1), 1-9.
- [47] Čegovnik, T., Stojmenova, K., Jakus, G., & Sodnik, J. (2018). An analysis of the suitability of a low-cost eye tracker for assessing the cognitive load of drivers. *Applied ergonomics*, 68, 1-11.

(a) Web static contents stimuli from eye tracking gaze

(b) Pupil dilation in synch with fixations and saccades

FIGURE 3 – A screenshot from the experimental study showing pupillometry results and virtual pupil changes, as well as eye tracking, including the fixation points and saccades.

(a) Pupil Measure from Female Gender

(b) Pupil Measure from Male Gender

FIGURE 4 – The raw pupillometry measure from male and female gender

(a) Density in measure of pupil responses

(b) Response contrast between dilation and constriction

(c) Response measure of pupil constriction and dilation

FIGURE 5 – Probability in response distribution of pupil constriction and dilation

FIGURE 6 – Error in measurement and prediction of cognitive level in pupillary response and virtual pupil response (MovAfilter).